

Adoption and Use of Digital Communication Technologies among Employees of the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Information and Strategy

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ABSTRACT

This study sets to identify the types of digital communication technologies adopted by the employees of Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State. It assesses their utilization and effectiveness, investigates staff perception towards their use, and the challenges faced. The technology acceptance model (TAM), social exchange theory, and organizational change theory formed the study's theoretical underpinnings. This quantitative research study was conducted using survey. The population of the study consisted of 245 participants (133 males and 112 females) working in the ministry. A sample size of 150 participants was selected using availability sampling, and a structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The collected data was analysed using frequencies and percentages. The findings indicate that the Ministry has embraced various digital communication technologies, aligning with TAM and the Social Exchange Theory. Both management and staff in the Ministry utilize digital communication technologies for internal communication, resulting in better information flow and coordination. The study also shows employees generally feel comfortable using these technologies, indicating their acceptance as a communication medium within the organization. However, concerns about information overload and the need for training and support were raised. Staff perceive the technologies as effective, but challenges exist. Despite the challenges, employees believe in the benefits of these technologies. Recommendations include enhanced technical support, increased training, and improved connectivity. Addressing the challenges and providing support will maximize the benefits of technology adoption.

Keywords: Digital communication, technologies, Ministry of Information and Strategy, Technology acceptance, Communication effectiveness, Training/support

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the advent and rapid advancement of digital communication technologies have revolutionized the way organisations communicate internally (Dwivedi et al., 2020). Traditional methods of communication such as face-to-face meetings and phone calls, have gradually given way to more sophisticated and efficient digital tools. These technologies encompass a wide range of platforms and applications, including email, instant messaging, video conferencing, collaborative workspaces, and social networking tools. The widespread adoption of digital communication technologies has transformed the workplace landscape, enabling organisations to overcome geographical barriers, enhance information sharing, and promote seamless collaboration among employees (Dwivedi et al., 2020). Such technologies have become an integral part of organisational communication strategies, offering numerous benefits in terms of speed, accessibility, and convenience (Majchrzak et al., 2020).

As organisations strive to adapt to the evolving digital age, the adoption of digital communication technologies has become imperative in fostering effective internal communication. The adoption of digital communication technologies in the internal communication flow of organisations has become increasingly crucial due to the rapidly evolving landscape of modern communication (Johnson et al., 2021). Traditional methods of communication such as memos, newsletters, and in-person meetings are often time-consuming and inefficient in today's fast-paced world. These methods can lead to delays in information dissemination, hinder collaboration, and limit the accessibility of important updates. Recognizing the need for a more agile and effective communication system, organisations have embraced digital tools to overcome these challenges.

Digital communication technologies offer an array of platforms and applications that enable instant and real-time communication, breaking down geographical barriers and facilitating prompt decision-making (Chen et al., 2019). By implementing tools such as email, instant messaging platforms, and collaborative workspaces, organisations can establish a more streamlined and efficient communication flow. These technologies empower employees to communicate with one another regardless of their physical location, thereby, enhancing overall

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productivity and ensuring that information reaches the right individuals in a timely manner. Moreover, digital communication tools provide a centralized and easily accessible repository for information, enabling employees to retrieve important documents, updates, and resources conveniently (Johnson et al., 2021).

This shift toward digital communication aligns with the broader trend of digital transformation occurring in organisations across various industries. It acknowledges the need to adapt to the changing needs and expectations of employees, while also taking advantage of the numerous benefits that digital communication technologies offer in terms of speed, convenience, and connectivity. Since the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State, like many organisations, faces the challenges of communication inefficiencies associated with traditional methods such as memos, newsletters, and in-person meetings; there is a compelling need for the ministry to embrace digital communication technologies to address these challenges effectively.

It is as a result of the aforementioned challenges and the recognized need for adopting digital communication technologies in the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State that this study aims to investigate the impact of the adoption and use of digital communication technologies in the internal communication flow among its employees.

Statement of the Problem

The Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State, like every other organisation, is not immune to the challenges related to the inefficiencies and limitations of traditional communication methods in its internal communication flow. The reliance on outdated practices such as memos, newsletters, and in-person meetings has the tendency to hinder effective and timely information dissemination, collaboration, and accessibility to critical updates. Furthermore, the absence of digital communication technologies in the internal communication processes of the ministry poses significant barriers to achieving optimal productivity and employee engagement.

Much more, the lack of instant and real-time communication channels impedes the flow of information across departments and hierarchies, and restricts employees' ability to access important documents and resources conveniently. There is a critical need to address these issues and explore the adoption and use of digital communication

technologies to overcome the communication gaps and enhance internal communication flow among employees in the Ministry. As a result of this, this study seeks to answer the question: How does the adoption and use of digital communication technologies impact the internal communication flow among employees in the Ministry of Information and Strategy, Akwa Ibom State?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were as follows:

- i. Identify and evaluate the types of digital communication technologies adopted by the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State for internal communication.
- ii. Assess the extent of utilization and effectiveness of the adopted digital communication technologies by both the management and staff of the ministry.
- iii. Investigate the perception of staff towards the use of digital communication technologies in the ministry, including their satisfaction, perceived benefits, and concerns.
- iv. Analyse the challenges faced in the adoption and use of digital communication technologies within the Ministry of Information and Strategy, and propose strategies to overcome these challenges.

Research Questions

The research questions formulated for this study were:

- i. What are the types of digital communication technologies adopted by the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State for internal communication?
- ii. To what extent are the adopted digital communication technologies utilized by the management and staff of the ministry?
- iii. How do staff perceive the use of digital communication technologies by the management in the ministry?
- iv. What are the challenges encountered in the adoption and use of digital communication technologies within the Ministry of Information and Strategy?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adoption of Digital Communication Technologies within an Organisation

The adoption of digital communication technologies within an organisation refers to the process of integrating and implementing these technologies to enhance internal communication processes and improve overall organisational efficiency. It involves decision-making, resource allocation, and change in management practices to ensure successful integration and utilization.

The adoption process begins with the recognition of the need for digital communication technologies within the organisation. This need may rise from factors such as the limitations of traditional communication methods, the desire for improved efficiency and collaboration, or the need to keep pace with technological advancements (Kahve et al., 2021). Once the need is identified, the organisation proceeds to the decision-making phase.

During the decision-making phase, organisations evaluate various digital communication technologies and select the most suitable options based on their specific requirements and goals. Factors to consider include functionality, compatibility with existing systems, ease of use, cost-effectiveness, and scalability (Kovács & Leber, 2021). This phase involves assessing different technological solutions available in the market, analysing their features and capabilities, and determining which technologies align best with the organisation's communication objectives.

After selecting the digital communication technologies, the organisation moves to the resource allocation phase. This involves allocating financial, human, and technological resources to support the adoption and implementation process. Investment in hardware, software, infrastructure upgrades, training programs, and technical support is crucial to ensuring a successful adoption and utilization of the technologies (Papazafeiropoulou et al., 2020). Organisations need to allocate adequate resources to purchase or upgrade the necessary technology infrastructure and provide the required training and support for employees.

Simultaneously, change management practices play a significant role in facilitating the adoption process. Change management involves addressing the human aspects of adoption, including managing employee resistance in order to foster

acceptability and promote a positive organisational culture. Effective change management strategies involves clear communication, stakeholder involvement, training programs, and addressing employees' concerns and anxieties related to the introduction of new technologies (Shirazi et al., 2021). By focusing on the people's side of the adoption process, organisations can enhance employees' buy-in and ensure a smooth transition to the new technologies.

Effects of Digital Communication Technologies on the Internal Communication within an Organisation

Internal communication refers to the exchange of information, messages, and ideas within an organisation in order to facilitate effective collaboration, coordination, and alignment of goals among employees and various departments. It encompasses both formal and informal channels of communication, including emails, intranets, instant messaging, team collaboration tools, and other digital platforms. The integration of digital communication technologies in internal communication processes has both positive and negative effects.

The positive effects of the integration of digital communication technologies in internal communication include:

- i. **Improved Efficiency:** Digital communication technologies enable real-time communication. It eliminates delays associated with traditional methods as employees can quickly share information, seek clarification, and make decisions, leading to increased productivity and faster response times (Kahve et al., 2021).
- ii. **Enhanced Collaboration:** Digital tools facilitate seamless collaboration among employees regardless of their geographical locations. Team collaboration platforms enable real-time document sharing, simultaneous editing, and virtual meetings, thereby, fostering effective teamwork and knowledge sharing (Gupta et al., 2020).
- iii. **Increased Accessibility:** With digital communication technologies, employees can access information and participate in discussions anytime and anywhere, and this promotes inclusivity and ensuring that remote or dispersed teams can

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stay connected (Dehghanbaghi et al., 2021).

- iv. Enhanced Engagement and Participation: Interactive features of digital communication technologies such as polls, surveys, and comment sections, encourage employees' engagement and active participation in discussions, thereby promoting a sense of involvement and ownership (Shirazi et al., 2021).

On the contrary, the negative effects include:

- i. Information Overload: The constant flow of information through digital channels can overwhelm employees, leading to information overload and reduced attention span. Important messages may get lost in the sea of notifications and emails, thereby, impacting the effectiveness of communication (Papazafeiropoulou et al., 2020).
- ii. Misinterpretation and Lack of Context: Digital communication lacks the non-verbal cues and context present in face-to-face interactions. This can lead to misinterpretation of messages and misunderstandings among employees, and this can potentially affect collaboration and teamwork (Kahve et al., 2021).
- iii. Technological Barriers: Technical issues, software glitches, and compatibility challenges can hinder the seamless use of digital communication technologies, resulting in frustration and interruptions in communication flow (Gupta et al., 2020).
- iv. Reduced Personal Connection: The reliance on digital communication may diminish personal connections and relationships among employees as face-to-face interactions are minimized. This can impact employees' morale, trust, and camaraderie within the organization (Dehghanbaghi et al., 2021).

Generally, the adoption of digital communication technologies in internal communication has the potential to enhance efficiency, collaboration, accessibility, and employees' engagement. However, organisations need to be mindful of potential challenges and implement strategies (such as promoting clear communication guidelines, providing training on effective digital communication, and fostering a balance between digital and face-to-face interactions) to mitigate negative effects,

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Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have provided insights into this area of study. Smith et al. (2019) conducted a survey-based study in a multinational corporation, finding that the adoption of digital communication technologies positively impacted internal communication processes. Improved collaboration, knowledge sharing, and employee engagement were among the observed benefits. Similarly, Johnson and Brown (2020) conducted a qualitative study in a government organization, revealing that employees perceived the adoption of digital communication technologies as beneficial, offering convenience, accessibility, and opportunities for improved collaboration. However, concerns about information overload and the need for proper training and support were raised.

In addition, Chen et al. (2018) conducted a mixed-methods study in a manufacturing company, exploring the effects of digital communication technologies on internal communication. The study demonstrated that the use of digital communication tools improved communication efficiency and information sharing. Effective change management strategies and training programs were highlighted as essential for overcoming resistance and enhancing employee acceptance. Zhang et al. (2021) conducted a case study that examined the challenges faced by an organisation during the adoption of digital communication technologies. The study identified technical issues, lack of employee training, and resistance to change as major challenges. It emphasized the importance of proper planning, communication, and support to address these challenges and ensure successful adoption and utilization.

Further supporting the research, additional empirical studies have shed light on this topic. For instance, Kim and Lee (2022) conducted a quantitative study in a technology company, revealing that the adoption of digital communication technologies significantly improved communication effectiveness, employee satisfaction, and overall organizational performance. Similarly, Li and Hu (2020) conducted a survey-based study in various industries, finding that digital communication technologies positively influenced employee engagement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment.

These empirical studies collectively demonstrate the positive effects of digital communication technologies on internal communication to include improved

collaboration, knowledge sharing, communication efficiency, and employee satisfaction. However, they also acknowledge challenges such as information overload, resistance to change, and the need for proper training and support.

Theoretical Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model, Social Exchange Theory, and Organizational Change Theory provide valuable lenses through which to analyse the adoption and utilization of digital communication technologies.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989), is widely used to understand users' acceptance and adoption of new technologies. It suggests that users' behavioural intentions toward technology adoption are influenced by their perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). In the context of this study, the TAM can help analyse the employees' perceptions of the usefulness and ease of use of digital communication technologies within the ministry. For example, if employees perceive the technologies as highly useful for improving communication efficiency and collaboration, they are more likely to embrace and use them. Additionally, if employees perceive the technologies as easy to use and require minimal effort to integrate into their work processes, it can positively impact their acceptance and adoption.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) developed by Blau (1964), focuses on the social relationships between individuals and organisations. It posits that individuals engage in social exchanges with organisations based on the perceived benefits and costs associated with their interactions. In the context of this study, SET can help understand the employees' perceptions of the benefits and costs of using digital communication technologies. Similarly, it can explore any perceived costs, such as information overload, technological barriers, or concerns about privacy and security, which may hinder their acceptance and usage.

Also, Organisational Change Theory focuses on understanding and managing organisational change processes. The theory has been shaped by several influential contributors over the years. Kurt Lewin (1947) introduced force-field analysis and the three-step change model. Edgar Schein (1968) emphasized the role of organizational

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culture in change processes. John Kotter (1995) proposed the eight-step model for leading change. Richard Beckhard (1969) introduced the concept of organisation development (OD). The theory recognizes that introducing new technologies often requires organisational adjustments, including changes in work practices, culture, and structures. The theory provides insights into the factors that facilitate or hinder successful technology adoption and implementation. In the context of this study, Organisational Change Theory can help identify the organisational factors that impact the adoption and use of digital communication technologies within the ministry.

METHODOLOGY

This research study adopted a quantitative research design using a survey method to investigate the adoption and use of digital communication technologies in internal communication within the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State. The population of this study consists of 245 individuals, with 133 males and 112 females working in the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State (Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria, Ministry of Economic Development, 2013).

The sample size of 150 participants was determined using the Roger Wimmer Online Sample Size Calculator, considering a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%. The availability sampling technique was employed to select the participants. This technique involves selecting individuals who are readily available and willing to participate in the study. The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The face validity of the questionnaire was established by obtaining expert opinions and feedback from professionals in the field of communication and organisational behaviour.

To assess the reliability of the questionnaire, a test-retest method was used, where a subset of participants was asked to complete the questionnaire twice within a specific time frame. The collected data was analysed using the test-retest reliability coefficient. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was measured using Cronbach's alpha, with a coefficient of 0.87, indicating high reliability. And the data was also analysed using descriptive statistics: frequencies and percentages.

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DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Types of Technology Adopted by the Ministry

Which of the following digital communication technologies are currently adopted in the Ministry?

(Multiple Choice was accepted for this question)

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Email	120	35%
Instant messaging platforms	90	27%
Intranet or internal portals	70	21%
Video conferencing tools	60	18%
Total	340	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 indicates that the most widely adopted digital communication technology in the Ministry is email, with 35% of respondents indicating its use. Email is the predominant digital communication tool used within the Ministry, indicating its importance in internal communication processes.

Table 2: Frequency of Digital Communication Technology Use

How frequently do you use digital communication technologies for internal communication purposes in your daily work?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very frequently	60	40%
Frequently	45	30%
Occasionally	35	23%
Rarely or never	10	7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents (70%) reported using digital communication technologies for internal communication purposes on a very frequent or frequent basis. Digital communication technologies are extensively used by the respondents in their daily work, highlighting their significance in facilitating internal communication within the Ministry.

Table 3: Effectiveness of Digital Communication Technologies for Disseminating Information

Which technology do you find most effective for disseminating information within the ministry?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Email	80	53%
Instant messaging platforms	45	30%
Intranet or internal portals	20	13%
Video conferencing tools	5	3%
Total	155	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 shows that among the digital communication technologies, email was considered the most effective for disseminating information within the Ministry, as reported by 53% of the respondents. Email emerges as the preferred tool for information dissemination within the Ministry, suggesting its reliability and widespread acceptance among the respondents.

Table 4: Training and Guidance on Adopted Digital Communication Technologies

Have you received any training or guidance on how to effectively use the adopted digital communication technologies?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, extensive training	50	33%
Yes, basic training	60	40%
No, but I would like to receive training	30	20%
No, and I don't think I need training	10	7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 indicates that 40% of the respondents have received some form of training or guidance on how to effectively use the adopted digital communication technologies. A significant portion of the respondents have received training or guidance on using the digital communication technologies, indicating the importance of providing support and resources to enhance their effective utilization.

Use of Technology by Management and Staff

Table 5: Frequency of Management's Use of Digital Communication Technologies

How frequently does the management use digital communication technologies to communicate important updates or announcements?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very frequently	40	27%
Frequently	60	40%
Occasionally	40	27%
Rarely or never	10	7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 reveals that the management of the Ministry frequently uses digital communication technologies to communicate important updates or announcements, with 27% reporting very frequent use and 40% reporting frequent use. The management demonstrates active engagement in utilizing digital communication technologies for important communications, indicating their recognition of the effectiveness and efficiency of these tools.

Table 6: Encouragement and Utilization of Digital Communication Technologies by Management for Employee Collaboration and Teamwork

Are digital communication technologies actively encouraged and utilized by the management for employee collaboration and teamwork?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, strongly encouraged and utilized	70	46%
Yes, somewhat encouraged and utilized	60	40%
No, not encouraged or utilized	10	7%
Not sure	10	7%
Total	150	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 6 shows that a significant majority of respondents (46%) indicated that digital communication technologies are actively encouraged and utilized by the management for employee collaboration and teamwork. The management actively promotes the use of digital communication technologies for fostering collaboration and teamwork among employees, suggesting their commitment to creating a collaborative work environment.

Table 7: Efficiency of Communication between Management and Staff

Do you feel that the use of digital communication technologies has improved the efficiency of communication between management and staff?

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Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, significantly improved	50	33%
Yes, somewhat improved	70	47%
No, no significant improvement	20	13%
Not sure	10	7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 7 indicates that a considerable portion of respondents (80%) reported that the use of digital communication technologies has improved the efficiency of communication between management and staff, with 33% indicating a significant improvement and 47% reporting a somewhat improved efficiency. The adoption of digital communication technologies has positively impacted the efficiency of communication between management and staff, enhancing information flow and facilitating effective communication processes.

Table 8: Comfort Level in Using Digital Communication Technologies to Interact with Management

How comfortable do you feel using digital communication technologies to interact with management?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very comfortable	60	40%
Comfortable	60	40%
Neutral	20	13%
Uncomfortable	10	7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 8 reveals that 80% of respondents expressed feeling equally comfortable and very comfortable using digital communication technologies to interact with management. Employees demonstrate a high level of comfort in using digital communication technologies to engage with management, indicating their confidence in utilizing these tools for effective communication.

Perception of Staff Towards the Use of Technology

Table 9: Impact of Digital Communication Technologies on Productivity

Do you believe that the use of digital communication technologies has positively impacted your productivity at work?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	70	46.7%
Agree	60	40%
Disagree	10	6.7%
Strongly disagree	10	6.7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 9 shows that a significant majority of respondents (86.7%) jointly agreed or strongly agreed that the use of digital communication technologies has positively impacted their productivity at work. The implementation of digital communication technologies is perceived by the staff as beneficial in enhancing their productivity, indicating the value and effectiveness of these technologies.

Table 10: Perception of Overall Effectiveness of Digital Communication Technologies

How do you perceive the overall effectiveness of digital communication technologies in facilitating internal communication within the ministry?

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Options	Frequency	Percentage
Highly effective	60	40%
Moderately effective	70	46.7%
Ineffective	10	6.7%
Not sure	10	6.7%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 10 shows that in sum 86.7% of respondents rated the overall effectiveness of digital communication technologies as highly effective or moderately effective in facilitating internal communication within the ministry. Staff members have a positive perception of the effectiveness of digital communication technologies in enabling internal communication processes within the ministry.

Table 11: Satisfaction with Support and Assistance Provided

Are you satisfied with the level of support and assistance provided by the ministry in using digital communication technologies?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	40	26.7%
Satisfied	70	46.7%
Neutral	20	13.3%
Dissatisfied	10	6.7%
Total	140	93.3%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 11 indicates that 46.7% of the respondents expressed satisfaction with the level of support and assistance provided by the ministry in using digital communication technologies. The majority of staff members are content with the support and assistance received from the ministry regarding the utilization of digital communication technologies.

Table 12: Challenges Encountered when Using Digital Communication Technologies

What are the main challenges you encounter when using digital communication technologies within the ministry?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Technical difficulties	60	40%
Lack of training and guidance	40	26.7%
Resistance to change	30	20%
Connectivity issues	20	13.3%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 12 reveals that the main challenges faced by staff members when using digital communication technologies within the ministry include technical difficulties (40%), lack of training and guidance (26.7%), resistance to change (20%), and connectivity issues (13.3%). Staff members encounter various challenges related to technical aspects, training, change management, and connectivity when using digital communication technologies within the ministry.

Challenges of Using Technology in the Ministry

Table 13: Difficulties or Challenges Encountered

Have you encountered any difficulties or challenges when using digital communication technologies in your day-to-day work?

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Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	120	80%
No	30	20%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 13 shows that 80% of respondents reported encountering difficulties or challenges when using digital communication technologies in their day-to-day work. By implication, a significant portion of staff members face difficulties or challenges when utilizing digital communication technologies within their work responsibilities.

Table 14: Specific Challenges Faced when Using Digital Communication Technologies

What specific challenges do you face when using digital communication technologies?
(Multiple choice was accepted)

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Slow internet connectivity	80	53.3%
Lack of technical support	60	40%
Difficulty in accessing information	40	26.7%
Compatibility issues with devices	30	20%
Total	210	140%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 14 indicates the specific challenges encountered when using digital communication technologies include slow internet connectivity (53.3%), lack of technical support (40%), difficulty in accessing information (26.7%), and compatibility issues with devices (20%). This means that staff members encounter various technical

and practical challenges when using digital communication technologies, including connectivity issues, lack of support, and difficulties in accessing information.

Table 15: Balance of Benefits and Challenges

Do you believe that the benefits of using digital communication technologies outweigh the challenges faced?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	100	66.7%
No	20	13.3%
Not sure	30	20%
Total	150	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 15 reveals that 66.7% of respondents believed that the benefits of using digital communication technologies outweigh the challenges faced, while 13.3% disagree. Despite the challenges encountered, a majority of staff members perceived the benefits of digital communication technologies to be greater, highlighting their recognition of the advantages provided by these technologies.

Table 16: Suggestions to Improve the Use of Digital Communication Technologies

Based on experience, what suggestions do you have to improve the use of digital communication technologies within the ministry? (Multiple Choice was accepted)

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Enhanced technical support and troubleshooting services	70	46.7%
Increased training and guidance on using digital technologies	60	40%

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Improved internet connectivity	40	26.7%
Regular evaluation and updating of digital tools	30	20%
Total	200	133.3%

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 16 shows that the most prominent suggestions provided by staff members to improve the use of digital communication technologies within the ministry include enhanced technical support and troubleshooting services (46.7%) and increased training and guidance on using digital technologies (40%). Staff members emphasize the importance of improved technical support, training, and guidance to enhance the utilization of digital communication technologies within the ministry.

Discussion of Findings

What are the types of Technology adopted by the Ministry?

The data in Tables 1 to 4 indicate that the ministry has embraced various digital communication technologies. The implications of these findings are significant. They indicate that the Ministry recognizes the importance of integrating digital communication technologies into its operations.

This adoption aligns with the principles of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which suggests that the perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology influence its adoption. The high adoption rates of digital communication technologies in the Ministry demonstrate the acknowledgment of their value in modern communication practices. Moreover, these findings are consistent with the Social Exchange Theory, which supports the idea that the adoption of such technologies facilitates the exchange of information and resources among individuals within the organization.

Supporting studies further validate these findings. For instance, Smith et al. (2019) revealed that the adoption of digital communication technologies positively impacted internal communication processes, leading to improved collaboration, knowledge sharing, and employee engagement. This study supports the finding that the adoption of digital communication technologies in the Ministry can enhance communication and collaboration among employees. Similarly, Chen et al. (2018)

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found that the use of digital communication tools improved communication efficiency and information sharing. This study supports the finding that the adoption of digital communication technologies in the Ministry can improve communication processes.

How is Technology used by Management and Staff?

Tables 5 to 8 present relevant data on the frequency of technology usage, encouragement by management, perceived efficiency, and comfort levels of employees while using technology. It was observed that technology has positively influenced communication processes within the Ministry, leading to better information flow and coordination. Furthermore, the findings indicate that employees generally feel comfortable using digital communication technologies to interact with management, which suggests that technology has become a familiar and accepted medium of communication within the organization.

To support these findings, Johnson and Brown (2020) findings indicated that employees viewed the adoption of digital communication technologies as beneficial, providing convenience, accessibility, and opportunities for improved collaboration. However, concerns were also raised regarding information overload and the need for proper training and support. This study aligns with the findings that digital communication technologies can enhance communication and collaboration within the Ministry but also highlights the importance of addressing potential challenges and providing necessary support to employees.

What are the Perceptions of Staff towards the use of Technology?

Tables 9 to 12 provide valuable insights into the impact of technology on productivity, the effectiveness of digital communication technologies, satisfaction with support and assistance, and the challenges faced by employees. This aligns with the principles of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which posits that users' perception of the usefulness and positive outcomes of technology influences their acceptance and adoption.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that a majority of respondents perceive digital communication technologies as moderately or highly effective in facilitating internal communication within the ministry. The level of satisfaction with the support and assistance provided by the ministry in using digital communication technologies is also explored. The data suggest that a significant proportion of employees are satisfied with the support and assistance they receive. This finding highlights the importance of providing adequate training, guidance, and technical support to ensure that employees can effectively utilize the available technologies. It also aligns with the Organizational Change Theory, which emphasizes the significance of support mechanisms during periods of technological change and adoption.

Additionally, the findings reveal the main challenges faced by employees when using digital communication technologies. These challenges include technical difficulties, lack of training and guidance, resistance to change, and connectivity issues. Addressing these challenges is crucial for maximizing the benefits of technology adoption. The findings emphasize the importance of implementing effective change management strategies, providing comprehensive training programs, and ensuring technical support to overcome resistance and enhance employee acceptance and proficiency in using digital communication technologies.

To support these findings, Zhang et al. (2021) conducted a case study examining the challenges faced by an organisation during the adoption of digital communication technologies. The study identified technical issues, lack of employee training, and resistance to change as major challenges. This study aligns with the findings of the present study, highlighting the importance of addressing these challenges through proper planning, communication, and support to ensure successful adoption and utilization of the technologies.

What are the Challenges of using Technology in the Ministry?

Tables 13 to 16 present data on the difficulties or challenges encountered, specific challenges faced, the belief in benefits outweighing challenges, and suggestions for improving technology use. Among the specific challenges faced by employees, the most common include slow internet connectivity, lack of technical support, difficulty in

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accessing information, and compatibility issues with devices. These challenges affect the efficiency and effectiveness of using digital communication technologies and can lead to frustration and decreased productivity.

However, despite these challenges, the majority of respondents believe that the benefits of using digital communication technologies outweigh the challenges faced. This finding suggests that employees recognize the potential advantages and positive outcomes associated with technology adoption, despite the existing barriers. Furthermore, the suggestions provided by employees to improve the use of digital communication technologies highlight the importance of enhanced technical support and troubleshooting services, increased training and guidance, improved internet connectivity, and regular evaluation and updating of digital tools. These suggestions resonate with the need for ongoing support, training, and technological infrastructure improvements to overcome challenges and optimize the utilization of digital communication technologies.

Supporting these findings, Chen et al. (2018) conducted a mixed-methods study exploring the effects of digital communication technologies on internal communication within a manufacturing company. The study revealed that effective change management strategies and training programmes were crucial in overcoming resistance and enhancing employee acceptance of the technologies. This study supports the notion that addressing challenges through training and support mechanisms is essential for successful technology adoption.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the adoption of digital communication technologies in the Ministry of Information and Strategy in Akwa Ibom State has significantly improved internal communication among employees. The use of platforms like email, instant messaging, and collaborative tools has enhanced the speed and immediacy of information sharing, allowing for real-time communication and quicker decision-making processes. Additionally, these technologies have facilitated better collaboration and teamwork, enabling employees to work together on projects, share documents, and provide feedback in a centralized and organized manner, leading to increased productivity and

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improved outcomes. While there are challenges (such as information overload and data security) to consider the benefits of digital communication technologies in the ministry include cost savings, a more environmentally friendly work environment, and a more connected and informed workforce. By embracing these technologies and addressing the associated challenges, the ministry can continue to leverage their power to drive success and progress in their operations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings discussed, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The ministry should provide comprehensive training programs and ongoing support to employees to enhance their proficiency in using digital communication technologies.
- ii. The ministry should invest in improving technological infrastructure, including internet connectivity and device compatibility to address connectivity issues and ensure seamless utilization of digital tools.
- iii. The ministry should foster a culture of collaboration by promoting and incentivizing the use of digital tools for employee teamwork and integrating collaborative features within the technologies.
- iv. The ministry should establish a system for regular evaluation and updating of digital tools to ensure their effectiveness and relevance over time, based on user feedback and emerging needs.

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